

COMMON FIXED POINT RESULT FOR GENERALIZED α_* - ψ -CONTRACTION FOR C -CLASS FUNCTIONS IN b -METRIC SPACES

TAIEB HAMAIZIA* AND SAID BELOUL

ABSTRACT. In this paper, we prove common fixed point theorems for α_* - ψ -contraction in b -metric spaces, which generalizes the result of S. Aleksic et al [Remarks on common fixed point results for generalized α_* - ψ -contraction multivalued mappings in b -metric spaces ,Adv. Fixed Point Theory, 9 (2019), No. 1, 1-16] using the concept of C class function in b -in metric spaces. An example is given to support our results.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Banach contraction principle [9] is the simplest and one of the important results in fixed point theory, that is, every contractive mapping T from a complete metric space (X, d) into itself has a unique fixed point z of the mapping T ($Tz = z$). Sufficient number of authors extended and generalize the concept of a metric space as b -metric spaces, fuzzy metric spaces, Menger metric spaces, quasi metric spaces...

Metric type spaces (or b -metric spaces) is one of the important generalization of metric spaces. This concept was introduced by Bakhtin 1989 [8] and Czerwik 1993 [11].

On the other hand, Nadler [22] introduced the notion of a multi-valued contractive mapping in a complete metric space and also proved Banach's fixed point theorem for a multi-valued mapping in a complete metric space. Moreover many authors proved some fixed point theorems for single-valued and multi-valued mappings in b -metric spaces, we refer the reader to ([1], [3], [6], [7], [10], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [19], [20], [21], [23]).

Motivated by the results and notions mentioned above. In this paper, we present new type contractions involving C -class functions and establish several common fixed point theorems for this class of mappings defined on b -metric spaces. Our main result is essentially inspired by S. Aleksic et al [2].

2. PRELIMINARIES

We appeal the following notions and preliminaries.

2010 *Mathematics Subject Classification.* 54E50, 58J20, 46J10.

Key words and phrases. b -metric space; Common fixed point; C -class function.

Received: April 29, 2021. Accepted: July 20, 2021. Published: September 30, 2021.

*Corresponding author.

Definition 2.1. Let X be a (nonempty) set and $s > 1$ be a given real number. A function $d : X \times X \rightarrow [0, 1)$ is a b -metric on X if for all $x, y, z \in X$, the following conditions hold:

- (b1) $d(x, y) = 0$ if and only if $x = y$,
- (b2) $d(x, y) = d(y, x)$,
- (b3) $d(x, z) \leq s[d(x, y) + d(y, z)]$.

A triplet (X, d, s) is called a b -metric space.

Also, every metric space is a b -metric space but the converse is not necessarily true.

Lemma 2.1. Let (X, d) be a b -metric space. The following properties are satisfied.

- 1) $D(x, B) \leq d(x, b)$ for all $x \in X, b \in B$ and $B \in CB(X)$.
- 2) $D(x, B) \leq H(A, B)$ for all $x \in X$ and $A, B \in CB(X)$.
- 3) $D(x, A) \leq s(d(x, y) + D(y, B))$ for all $x, y \in X$ and $A, B \in CB(X)$.

Let (X, d) be a metric space and $\alpha : X \times X \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ be a given mapping. A mapping $T : X \rightarrow CL(X)$ is an

- (1) α_* -admissible, if $\alpha(x, y) \geq 1$ implies $\alpha_*(Tx, Ty) \geq 1$, where $\alpha_*(Tx, Ty) = \inf \{\alpha(a, b) : a \in Tx, b \in Ty\}$;
- (2) α -admissible, if for each $x \in X$ and $y \in Tx$ with $\alpha(x, y) \geq 1$, we have $\alpha(y, z) \geq 1$ for all $z \in Ty$.

Definition 2.2. [4] Let $S, T : X \rightarrow CB(X)$ be two multi-valued mappings and $\alpha : X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ a function.

The pair (S, T) is said to be triangular α_* -admissible if the following conditions hold:

- 1) (S, T) is α_* -admissible, that is, $\alpha(x, y) \geq 1$ implies that $\alpha_*(Sx, Ty) \geq 1$ and $\alpha_*(Tx, Sy) \geq 1$; where $\alpha_*(A, B) = \inf \{\alpha(x, y) / x \in A, y \in B\}$,
- 2) $\alpha(x, u) \geq 1$ and $\alpha(u, y) \geq 1$ imply $\alpha(x, y) \geq 1$:

Definition 2.3. [4] Let $S, T : X \rightarrow CB(X)$ be two multi-valued mappings and $\alpha : X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ a function. The pair (S, T) is said to be α_* -orbital admissible if the conditions $\alpha_*(x, Sx) \geq 1$ and $\alpha_*(x, Tx) \geq 1$ imply $\alpha_*(Sx, T^2x) \geq 1$ and $\alpha_*(Tx, S^2x) \geq 1$.

Definition 2.4. [4] Let $S, T : X \rightarrow CB(X)$ be two multi-valued mappings and $\alpha : X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ a function. The pair (S, T) is said to be triangular α_* -orbital admissible if the following conditions are satisfied :

- 1) (S, T) is α_* -orbital admissible,
- 2) $\alpha(x, y) \geq 1, \alpha_*(y, Sy) \geq 1$ and $\alpha_*(y, Ty) \geq 1$ implies that $\alpha_*(x, Sy) \geq 1$ and $\alpha_*(x, Ty) \geq 1$

Lemma 2.2. [22] If $A, B \in CB(X)$ and $k > 1$, then for each $a \in A$, there exists $b \in B$ such that $d(a, b) \leq kH(A, B)$.

A. H. Ansari [5] introduced the concept of a C -class functions which covers a large class of contractive conditions

Definition 2.5. [5] A continuous function $F : [0, \infty)^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called C -class function if for any $s, t \in [0, \infty)^2$; the following conditions hold

- c1 $F(s, t) \leq s$;
- c2 $F(s, t) = s$ implies that either $s = 0$ or $t = 0$.

An extra condition on F that $F(0, 0) = 0$ could be imposed in some cases if required. The letter C will denote the class of all C - functions.

Example 2.6. The following examples shows that the class C is nonempty:

1. $F(s, t) = s - t$.
2. $F(s, t) = ms$, for some $m \in (0, 1)$.
3. $F(s, t) = \frac{s}{(1+t)^r}$, for some $r \in (0, 1)$.
4. $F(s, t) = \frac{\log(t+a^s)}{(1+t)}$, for some $a > 1$.

Let u denote the class of the functions $\varphi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ which satisfy the following conditions:

- a) φ is continuous ;
- b) $\varphi(t) > 0$, $t > 0$ and $\varphi(0) \geq 0$.

In 1984, Khan et al. [18] introduced altering distance function as follows:

Definition 2.7. [18] A function $\psi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is called an altering distance function if the following properties are satisfied:

- i) ψ is non-decreasing and continuous,
- ii) $\psi(t) = 0$ if and only if $t = 0$.

Let us suppose that Ψ denote the class of the altering distance functions.

Definition 2.8. A tripled (ψ, φ, F) where $\psi \in \Psi$; $\varphi \in \Phi_u$ and $F \in C$ is said to be a monotone if for any $x, y \in [0, \infty)$;

$$x \leq y \Rightarrow F(\psi(x), \varphi(x)) \leq F(\psi(y), \varphi(y)).$$

Example 2.9. Let $F(s, t) = s - t$, $\varphi(x) = \sqrt{x}$

$$\psi(x) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{x} & \text{if } 0 \leq x \leq 1 \\ x^2 & \text{if } x > 1 \end{cases},$$

then (ψ, φ, F) is monotone.

Example 2.10. Let $F(s, t) = s - t$, $\varphi(x) = x^2$

$$\psi(x) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{x} & \text{if } 0 \leq x \leq 1 \\ x^2 & \text{if } x > 1 \end{cases},$$

then (ψ, φ, F) is monotone.

Example 2.11. Let $F(s, t) = \frac{s}{1+t}$, $\varphi(x) = \sqrt[3]{x}$

$$\psi(x) = \begin{cases} \sqrt[3]{x} & \text{if } 0 \leq x \leq 1 \\ x^3 & \text{if } x > 1 \end{cases},$$

then (ψ, φ, F) is monotone.

Example 2.12. Let $F(s, t) = \log\left(\frac{t+e^s}{1+t}\right)$, $\varphi(x) = e^x$ and $\psi(x) = x$

then (ψ, φ, F) is monotone.

Example 2.13. Let $F(s, t) = s - t$, $\varphi(x) = x^3$

$$\psi(x) = \begin{cases} \sqrt[3]{x} & \text{if } 0 \leq x \leq 1 \\ x^3 & \text{if } x > 1 \end{cases},$$

then (ψ, φ, F) is monotone.

3. MAIN RESULTS

Firstly, in this section we assume ψ is altering distance function, φ is ultra altering distance function and F is a C -class function.

Theorem 3.1. Let $(X, d, s > 1)$ be a b -metric space, $\alpha : X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ a function and $\varepsilon > 1$. Let $S, T : X \rightarrow CB(X)$ be two multi-valued mappings such that for $x, y \in X$; with $\alpha(x, y) \geq 1$;

the pair (S, T) satisfies the inequality

$$\psi(s^\varepsilon \cdot H(Sx, Ty)) \leq F(\psi(M(x, y)), \varphi(M(x, y))) \quad (3.1)$$

where

$$M(x, y) = \max \left\{ d(x, y), D(x, Sx), D(y, Ty), \frac{D(x, Ty) + D(y, Sx)}{2s} \right\}.$$

Suppose that the following conditions are satisfied.

(i) (X, d) is an α -complete b -metric space.

(ii) (S, T) is triangular α_* -orbital admissible.

(iii) There exists $x_0 \in X$ such that $\alpha_*(x_0, Sx_0) \geq 1$.

(iv) S and T are α -continuous multi-valued mappings, or, if $\{x_n\}$ a sequence in X which converges to $x \in X$ such that $\alpha(x_n, x_{n+1}) \geq 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then there exists a subsequence $\{x_{n_k}\}$ satisfies $\alpha(x_{n_k}, x)$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Then S and T have a common fixed point.

Proof. From (iii), there exists $x_1 \in Sx_0$ such that $\alpha_*(x_0, x_1) \geq 1$ and $x_1 \neq x_0$. By the inequality (3.1) and (2) in Lemma (2.1), we have

$$0 < \psi(s^\varepsilon D(x_1, Tx_1)) \leq \psi(s^\varepsilon \cdot H(Sx_0, Tx_1)) \leq F(\psi(M(x_0, x_1)), \varphi(M(x_0, x_1))). \quad (3.2)$$

Using Lemma (2.2) for

$$k = s^\varepsilon,$$

there exists $x_2 \in Tx_1$ such that

$$\psi(d(x_1, x_2)) \leq \psi(s^\varepsilon \cdot H(Sx_0, Tx_1)) \leq F(\psi(M(x_0, x_1)), \varphi(M(x_0, x_1))), \quad (3.3)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} M(x_0, x_1) &= \max \left\{ d(x_0, x_1), D(x_0, Sx_0), D(x_1, Tx_1), \frac{D(x_0, Tx_1) + D(x_1, Sx_0)}{2s} \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ d(x_0, x_1), D(x_1, Tx_1), \frac{D(x_0, Tx_1)}{2s} \right\} \\ &= \max \{d(x_0, x_1), D(x_1, Tx_1)\}. \end{aligned}$$

If $M(x_0, x_1) = D(x_1, Tx_1)$, then from (3.1), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &< \psi(D(x_1, Tx_1)) \leq \psi(s^\varepsilon D(x_1, Tx_1)) \leq \psi(s^\varepsilon \cdot H(Sx_0, Tx_1)) \\ &\leq F(\psi(D(x_1, Tx_1)), \varphi(D(x_1, Tx_1))) \\ &\leq \psi(D(x_1, Tx_1)). \end{aligned}$$

Since ψ is nondecreasing function, so $D(x_1, Tx_1) = 0$ which is a contradiction. Then

$$\max \{d(x_0, x_1), D(x_1, Tx_1)\} = d(x_0, x_1).$$

According to the inequality (3.1)

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(d(x_1, x_2)) &\leq \psi(s^\varepsilon \cdot H(Sx_0, Tx_1)) \leq F(\psi(d(x_0, x_1)), \varphi(d(x_0, x_1))) \\ &\leq \psi(d(x_0, x_1)). \end{aligned}$$

Since ψ is nondecreasing, we get

$$d(x_1, x_2) \leq d(x_0, x_1).$$

Similarly, for $x_2 \in Tx_1$, there exists $x_3 \in Sx_2$ such that

$$\psi(d(x_2, x_3)) \leq s^\varepsilon H(Tx_1, Sx_2)F(\psi(d(x_1, x_2)), \varphi(d(x_1, x_2))) \leq \psi(d(x_1, x_2)).$$

Repeating this process, we can construct a sequence $\{x_n\} \subset X$ as follows.

$$\begin{cases} x_{2k+1} \in Sx_{2k}, \\ x_{2k+2} \in Tx_{2k+1}, \quad \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

for $k = 1, 2, \dots$. Since (S, T) is is triangular $\alpha_{\Delta st}$ orbital admissible, so from lemma 2.2 we get $\alpha(x_n, x_{n+1}) \geq 1$. Hence we have

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(d(x_{2k+1}, x_{2k+2})) &\leq \psi(s^\varepsilon H(Tx_{2k}, Sx_{2k+1})) \\ &\leq F(\psi(M(x_{2k}, x_{2k+1})), \varphi(M(x_{2k}, x_{2k+1}))) \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} M(x_{2k}, x_{2k+1}) &= \max \left\{ d(x_{2k}, x_{2k+1}), \frac{D(x_{2k}, Sx_{2k}), D(x_{2k+1}, Tx_{2k+1})}{\frac{D(x_{2k}, Tx_{2k+1}) + D(x_{2k+1}, Sx_{2k})}{2s}}, \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ d(x_{2k}, x_{2k+1}), D(x_{2k+1}, Tx_{2k+1}), \frac{D(x_{2k}, Tx_{2k+1})}{2s} \right\} \\ &= \max \{d(x_{2k}, x_{2k+1}), D(x_{2k+1}, Tx_{2k+1})\} \end{aligned}$$

If $M(x_{2k}, x_{2k+1}) = D(x_{2k+1}, Tx_{2k+1})$, using (3.1), we get

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &< \psi(s^\varepsilon D(x_{2k+1}, Tx_{2k+1})) \leq \psi(s^\varepsilon .H(Sx_{2k}, Tx_{2k+1})) \\ &\leq F(\psi(D(x_{2k+1}, Tx_{2k+1})), \varphi(D(x_{2k+1}, Tx_{2k+1}))) \\ &\leq \psi(D(x_{2k+1}, Tx_{2k+1})), \end{aligned}$$

which is a contradiction. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(d(x_{2k+1}, x_{2k+2})) &\leq \psi(s^\varepsilon .H(Sx_{2k}, Tx_{2k+1})) \leq F(\psi(d(x_{2k}, x_{2k+1})), \varphi(d(x_{2k}, x_{2k+1}))) \\ &\leq \psi(d(x_{2k}, x_{2k+1})), \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

which implies

$$d(x_{2k+1}, x_{2k+2}) \leq d(x_{2k}, x_{2k+1}).$$

Thus for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have

$$d(x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}) \leq d(x_n, x_{n+1}),$$

this yields $\{d(x_n, x_{n+1})\}$ is decreasing sequence.

The non increasing of ψ hold the decreasing the sequence $\{d(x_{n+1}, x_n)\}$ such that

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x_n, x_{n+1}) = r$ Letting $n \rightarrow \infty$ in (3.5), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \psi(s^{1-\varepsilon} d(x_{n+2}, x_{n+1})) &\leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \psi(d(x_{n+2}, x_{n+1})) \\ &\leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} F(\psi(s^{1-\varepsilon} d(x_n, x_{n-1})), \varphi(s^{1-\varepsilon} d(x_n, x_{n+1}))) \\ &\leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \psi(s^{1-\varepsilon} d(x_n, x_{n+1})). \end{aligned}$$

So, we conclude that

$$\psi(s^{1-\varepsilon} r) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} F(\psi(s^{1-\varepsilon} r), \varphi(s^{1-\varepsilon} r)) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \psi(s^{1-\varepsilon} r).$$

For $s^{1-\varepsilon} \neq 0$, implies $r = 0$, a contradiction. Hence, we conclude

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x_n, x_{n+1}) = 0$$

Now, we prove that the sequence $\{x_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence. Suppose that the $\{x_{2n}\}$ is not a Cauchy sequence. Then there exists an $\varepsilon > 0$ for which we can find two sequences of positive integers $\{2m(k)\}$ and $\{2n(k)\}$ such that for all positive integers k , $2n(k) > 2m(k) > k$ and $d(x_{2m(k)}, x_{2n(k)}) \geq \varepsilon$.

Let $2n(k)$ be the smallest such positive integer $2n(k) > 2m(k) > k$ such that

$$d(x_{2m(k)}, x_{2n(k)}) \geq \varepsilon, \quad d(x_{2m(k)}, x_{2n(k)-1}) < \varepsilon$$

by (3.1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(s^{\varepsilon-1}d(x_{2m(k)}, x_{2n(k)})) &\leq F(\psi(M(x_{2n(k)-1}, x_{2m(k)})), \varphi(M(x_{2n(k)-1}, x_{2m(k)}))) \\ &= F(\psi(d(x_{2n(k)-1}, x_{2m(k)})), \varphi(d(x_{2n(k)-1}, x_{2m(k)}))) \end{aligned}$$

Letting $n \rightarrow \infty$ we have

$$\psi(\varepsilon) \leq \psi(s^{\varepsilon-1}\varepsilon) \leq F(\psi(\varepsilon), \varphi(\varepsilon)) \leq \psi(\varepsilon)$$

Then $\psi(\varepsilon) = 0$ contradiction with $\varepsilon > 0$. Thus (x_n) is a b -Cauchy sequence in X . α -completeness of (X, d) implies the existence of $z \in X$ such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x_n, z) = 0$$

which implies $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x_{2k+1}, z) = 0$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x_{2k+2}, z) = 0$.

If S, T are α -continuous, this gives $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} H(Tx_{2k+1}, z) = 0$.

Using triangular inequality we get

$$D(z, Tz) \leq s(d(x_{2k+1}, Tx_{2k}) + H(Tx_{2k+1}, Tz))$$

passing to limit we obtain $D(z, Tz) = 0$, this yields $z \in Tz$. Similarly we can show easily $z \in Sz$ and z is a common fixed point for S and T .

If for a sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X which converges to $x \in X$ such that $\alpha(x_n, x_{n+1}) \geq 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then there exists a subsequence $\{x_{n_k}\}$ satisfies $\alpha(x_{n_k}, x)$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Since $x_n \rightarrow z$, then there exists a sequence $\{x_{n_k}\}$ such that $\alpha(x_{n_k}, x)$, so we have

$$D(z, Tz) \leq s(d(x_{2k+1}, Tx_{2k}) + H(Tx_{2k+1}, Tz)).$$

This complete the proof. \square

The following results are a special case of the main result

Corollary 3.2. *Let (X, d) be a b -metric space, $\alpha : X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ a function and $\varepsilon > 1$. Let $S, T : X \rightarrow CB(X)$ be two multi-valued mappings such that for $x, y \in X$ with $\alpha(x, y) \geq 1$ we have*

$$\psi(s^\varepsilon H(Sx, Ty)) \leq \psi(M(x, y)) - \varphi(M(x, y)), \quad (3.6)$$

where

$$M(x, y) = \max \left\{ d(x, y), D(x, Sx), D(y, Ty), \frac{D(x, Ty) + D(y, Sx)}{2s} \right\}.$$

Then S and T have a common fixed point.

Corollary 3.3. *Let (X, d) be a b -metric space, $\alpha : X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ a function and $\varepsilon > 1$. Let $S, T : X \rightarrow CB(X)$ be two multi-valued mappings such that for $x, y \in X$ with $\alpha(x, y) \geq 1$ we have*

$$s^\varepsilon H(Sx, Ty) \leq \phi(M(x, y)), \quad (3.7)$$

where $\phi : [0, +\infty) \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ is a lower semi continuous function satisfying $\phi(t) = 0$ if and only if $t = 0$.

$$M(x, y) = \max \left\{ d(x, y), D(x, Sx), D(y, Ty), \frac{D(x, Ty) + D(y, Sx)}{2s} \right\}.$$

Then S and T have a common fixed point.

Proof. It suffices to taking $\psi = I$ and $\phi = I - \varphi$ in Theorem 3.1. \square

Example 3.1. Let $X = \{1, 2, 3\}$ and $d(x, y) = |x - y|^2$. Define $S, T: X \rightarrow CB(X)$ and $\alpha : X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ by

$$Sx = \begin{cases} \{2\}, & x \in \{1, 2\} \\ \{1\}, & x = 3 \end{cases}$$

$$Tx = \begin{cases} \{3\}, & x = 1 \\ \{2\}, & x \in \{2, 3\} \end{cases}$$

and

$$\alpha(x, y) = \begin{cases} 0, & (x, y) \in \{(3, 1)\} \\ 1, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

We claim that S and T satisfy (3.1), by taking $s = 2$, $F(m, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}m$, $\varepsilon = \frac{1}{2}$ and $\psi(t) = t$. For that, we need to show that

$$2^\varepsilon H(Sx, Ty) \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} M_s(x, y).$$

Note that $H(Tx, Ty) > 0$ and $\alpha(x, y) \geq 1$ if and only if $(x, y) \in X^2 - \{(2, 2), (1, 2), (1, 3), (2, 3), (3, 1)\}$.

(1) For $x = 1$ and $y = 1$, we have

$$H(S1, T1) = 1 \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} D(1, T1) = 2\sqrt{2}.$$

which implies

$$2^{\frac{1}{2}} H(S1, T1) \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} M(1, 1).$$

(2) For $x = 2$ and $y = 1$, we have

$$H(S2, T1) = 1 \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} D(1, T1) = 2\sqrt{2},$$

which implies

$$2^{\frac{1}{2}} H(S2, T1) \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} M(2, 1).$$

(3) For $x = 3$ and $y = 2$, we have

$$H(S3, T2) = 1 \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} D(3, S3) = 2\sqrt{2},$$

which implies

$$2^{\frac{1}{2}} H(S3, T2) \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} M(3, 2).$$

(4) For $x = 3$ and $y = 3$, we have

$$H(S3, T3) = 1 \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} D(3, S3) = 2\sqrt{2},$$

which implies

$$2^{\frac{1}{2}} H(S3, T3) \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} M(3, 3).$$

Consequently, S and T satisfy (3.1). Moreover, it is easy to see that (S, T) is triangular α_* -orbital admissible. Indeed

For $(x, y) \in \{1, 2\}$, we have

$$\alpha_*(x, Sx) = \alpha_*(x, Tx) = 1 \geq 1, \text{ and } \alpha_*(Sx, T^2x) = \alpha_*(Tx, S^2x) = 1 \geq 1,$$

then (S, T) is α_* -orbital admissible.

For $(x, y) \in \{1, 2\}$, we have

$$\alpha(x, y) = 1, \text{ and } \alpha_*(y, Sy) = \alpha_*(y, Ty) = 1 \geq 1.$$

and

$$\alpha_*(x, Sy) = \alpha_*(x, Ty) = 1 \geq 1.$$

Hence (S, T) is triangular α_* -orbital admissible, there exists $x_0 = 1 \in X$ such that $\alpha_*(1, S1) \geq 1$. Also, For $x_n = 1$, we have x_n converges to $1 \in X$, such that $\forall n \geq 0, \alpha(x_n, x_{n+1}) = \alpha(1, 1) = 1 \geq 1$, and $\alpha(x_n, 1) = 1 \geq 1$, so it suffices to choose $x_{n_k} = x_n, \forall \varepsilon > 0$. Consequently, all conditions of Theorem 3.1 are satisfied. Then T, S have a fixed point which is 2.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to the reviewers valuable comments that improved the manuscript.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Aghajani, M. Abbas and J.R. Roshan. Common fixed point of generalized weak contractive mappings in partially ordered b-metric spaces, *Math. Slovaca*, 4 (2014), 941–960.
- [2] S. Aleksic, T. Dosenovic, Z. D. Mitrovic and S. Radenovic. Remarks on common fixed point results for generalized α_* – ψ -contraction multivalued mappings in b-metric spaces, *Adv. Fixed Point Theory*, 9(1) (2019), 1–16.
- [3] A. Aliouche and T. Hamaizia. Common fixed point theorems for multivalued mappings in b-metric spaces with an application to integral inclusions. *The Journal of Analysis*, 2021, doi: 10.1186/s13660-017-1528-3.
- [4] E. Ameer, M. Arshad and W. Shatanawi. Common fixed point results for generalized α_* – ψ -contraction multivalued mappings in b-metric spaces, *J. Fixed Point Theory Appl.*, 19(4) (2017), 3069–3086.
- [5] A. H. Ansari. Note on φ - ψ -contractive type mappings and related fixed point”, *The 2nd regional conference on mathematics and applications*, Payame Noor University, 2014, p 377-380.
- [6] M. Arshad, E. Ameer and E. Karapinar. Generalized contractions with triangular α -orbital admissible mapping on Branciari metric spaces. *J Inequal. Appl.*, 2016, doi: 10.1186/s13660-016-1010-7.
- [7] H. Aydi, A. Felhi and S. Sahmim. Common fixed points in rectangular b-metric spaces using (E:A) property, *J. Adv. Math. Stud.*, 8(2) (2015), 159–169.
- [8] I. A. Bakhtin. The contraction principle in quasi metric spaces, *Funct. Anal.*, 30 (1989), 26–37.
- [9] S. Banach. Sur les oprations dans les ensembles abstraits et leur application aux quations intgrales, *Fund. Math.* 3 (1922), 133–181.
- [10] M. Boriceanu. Strict fixed point theorems for multivalued operators in b-metric spaces, *Int. J. Modern Math.*, 4 (2009), 285–301.
- [11] S. Czerwik. Contraction mappings in b-metric spaces, *Acta Math. Inform., Univ. Ostrav.*, 1 (1993), 5–11.
- [12] T. Hamaizia. Fixed point theorems for generalized (ψ, φ, F) -contraction type mappings in b-metric spaces with applications, *Open Journal of Mathematical Analysis*, 5(1) (2021), 35–41.
- [13] T. Hamaizia and A. Aliouche. A nonunique common fixed point theorem of Rhoades type in b-metric spaces with applications, *Int. J. Nonlinear Anal. Appl.*, 12(2) (2021), 399–413.
- [14] A. A. Harandi. Fixed point theory for quasi-contraction maps in b-metric spaces, *Fixed Point Theory* 15(2) (2014), 351–358.
- [15] N. Hussain, V. Parvaneh, J. R. Roshan and Z. Kadelburg. Fixed points of cyclic weakly (ψ, φ, L, A, B) -contractive mappings in ordered b-metric spaces with applications, *Fixed Point Theory Appl.*, 256 (2013), 1–18.

- [16] N. Hussain and Z. D. Mitrovic. On multivalued weak quasi-contractions in b -metric spaces, *J. Nonlinear Sci. Appl.*, 10 (2017), 3815–3823.
- [17] M. Jleli, B. Samet, C. Vetro and F. Vetro. Fixed points for multivalued mappings in b -metric spaces. *Abstr. Appl. Anal.*, 2015, doi: 10.1155/2015/718074.
- [18] M. S. Khan, M. Swaleh and S. Sessa. Fixed point theorems by altering distances between the points, *Bulletin of the Australian Mathematical Society*, 30(1) (1989), 1–9.
- [19] L. Liu and F. Gu. Common fixed point theorems for six self-maps in b -metric spaces with nonlinear contractive conditions, *J. Nonlinear Sci. Appl.* 9 (2016), 5909–5930.
- [20] S. Merdaci and T. Hamaizia. Some fixed point theorems of rational type contraction in b -metric spaces, *Moroccan J. of Pure and Appl. Anal.*, 7(3) (2021), 350–363.
- [21] R. Miculescu and A. Mihail. New fixed point theorems for set-valued contractions in b -metric spaces, *J. Fixed Point Theory Appl.*, 19(3) (2017), 2153–2163.
- [22] S. B. Nadler. Multi-valued contractions mappings, *Pacific J. Math.*, 30(2) (1969), 475–488.
- [23] W. Shatanawi and M. B. Hani. A fixed point theorem in b -metric spaces with nonlinear contractive condition. *Far East J. Math. Sci.* 100 (2016), 1901–1908.

TAIEB HAMAIZIA

LABORATORY OF DYNAMICAL SYSTEMS AND CONTROL, DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS AND INFORMATICS, LARBI BEN M'HIDI UNIVERSITY, OUM-EL-BOUAGHI, 04000, ALGERIA

Email address: tayeb042000@yahoo.fr

SAID BELOUL

FACULTY OF EXACT SCIENCE, EL-OUED UNIVERSITY, ALGERIA

Email address: beloulsaid@gmail.com